

Continuous Glucose Monitoring in a Patient with Pancreas Graft Thrombosis

Introduction

Pancreas graft artery thrombosis is a feared complication in the early posttransplant period, often diagnosed too late to preserve the graft. Using rtCGM could possibly help in earlier hyperglycaemia detection. We present rtCGM data from a patient in a perioperative rtCGM trial who suffered from graft artery thrombosis resulting in graftectomy 7 days post-transplant.

Methods

We retrospectively analysed CGM data obtained from a blinded CGM, Dexcom G6, during an ongoing prospective trial testing the accuracy and feasibility of CGM in postoperative intensive care. Sensor is inserted immediately after surgery, and kept throughout the ICU stay and, if possible, up to 10 days.

Results

50-year-old male with type 1 diabetes and advanced microvascular complications (neuropathy, proliferative retinopathy, nephropathy) was admitted for pancreas retransplantation. He had undergone simultaneous pancreas and kidney transplantation in 2011 and had lost his pancreas graft due to acute cellular rejection grade 3 refractory to anti-rejection treatment. He achieved normoglycaemia early post-transplant, with no need for insulin after switching from parenteral nutrition to oral food intake on day 3. Occasionally he had milder hyperglycaemia (11 mmol/l) after meals, which was attributed to corticosteroid therapy. He was recovering promptly, however suffered from epididymitis on day 3, treated with antibiotics. On day 7, severe abdominal pain occurred at night, abdominal ultrasound and subsequent CT showed arterial graft thrombosis with necrotic changes, leading to immediate graftectomy.

CGM data cover days 0 to 6 (when it was removed on patient request). Despite lacking the last day when the symptoms occurred, we captured postprandial hyperglycaemias especially in the afternoon starting on day 3, gradually worsening each day, daily time in hyperglycaemia rising from 9% on day 2 to 38% on day 6, average glycaemia rising from 7.3 ± 1.3 to 8.7 ± 2.7 mmol/l. These elevations were not adequately captured by frequent glucose meter measurements, his pre-prandial glycaemia levels were only mildly elevated.

Conclusion

This case study shows retrospectively captured hyperglycaemic patterns in a patient with pancreas graft thrombosis and brings a question of possible benefits of CGM use in early posttransplant period.

Supported by the project National Institute for Research of Metabolic and Cardiovascular Diseases (Programme EXCELES, ID Project No. LX22NPO5104) - Funded by the European Union – Next Generation EU